

CURBING YOUTH MIGRATION THROUGH SUSTAINABLE INDUSTRIALIZATION AND ECONOMIC EMPOWERMENT IN RIVERS STATE: THE ROLE OF TECHNICAL AND VOCATIONAL EDUCATION AND TRAINING PROGRAMMES

¹Ajie, Prince Maduabuchukwu (Ph.D), ²Bassey, Imaobong Sunday,
³Ojobah, Lucky Obulor (PhD)

Department of Metalwork Technology, Federal College of Education (Technical) Omoku, Rivers State Nigeria;

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11162693>

Published Date: 09-May-2024

Abstract: This study examined curbing youth migration through sustainable industrialization and economic empowerment in Rivers State; the role of technical and vocational education and training programmes. Specifically, this study sought to investigate the causes of youth migration to overseas; examine the youth economic empowerment role of TVET in curbing youth migration in Rivers State; and to identify the industrial role of TVET in curbing youth migration in Rivers State. Three research questions and hypotheses were answered and tested at 0.05 level of significance. A descriptive survey design guided the study. The population of the study comprised 100 technical education lecturers and 144 final year technical education students in the three tertiary institutions in Rivers State that offer TVET. The population was manageable, therefore, the entire population was used for the study, and hence no sampling technique was used for the study. Self-made survey questionnaire served as the instrument for the study. The instrument was face validated by two experts. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient which yielded a coefficient of 74. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions while z-test statistical tool was used to test the hypotheses. The study found among others that high poverty level, low economic performance, bad governance are the causes of youth migration while TVET improves the living condition and livelihood of the youths, creates employment in both rural and urban areas, equip youths with requisite knowledge, and skills to be engaged, transforms nation economy and creates platform for production. It was recommended among others that Nigerian leaders should cultivate a youth-friendly socioeconomic environment by providing technical know-how, resources for youth to thrive.

Keywords: Migration, TVET, Sustainable Industrialization, & Economic Empowerment.

1. INTRODUCTION

No country seeking economic development, which is the good and better life, can afford to neglect the youths, or abandon them to constitute major social problems. This is because the youths are the engine of economic growth and industrial development; they provide or serve as the source of the labour force for the production of goods and services. They are also

the critical masses of the people whose action and inaction can develop or destroy the fabrics of their country. In other words, they determine the future of the country (Uba & Chiwuike, 2022). The African Youth charter defined youth as any individual between 15 and 35 years of age. In Nigeria, the youth population accounts for over half of the projected national population of over 200 million people. Population growth and urbanization go together and economic development and growth is closely correlated with urbanization (Akinyemi & Mibolaji, 2022).

Nigeria has abundant and varied resources which portrays it as a rich nation. Most times these resources are mismanaged, pushing the inhabitants to extreme poverty. As the poverty is biting hard and the population is increasing, the people seek for various strategies to survive. One of such strategies is migration to the overseas. Smita & Mallah (2015) defined Migration as movement of an individual or people between regions or countries. It is the process of moving from the use of one operating environment to other operating environment that is, in most cases, is thought to be a better one. Migration may be temporary, with the intention of returning to the country of origin in the future or permanent.

The Nigerian emigration experience can be divided into four eras: the civil and political unrest stages of the 1960s; the downfall of the petroleum boom in the 1980s; the military regime of the mid-1990s and the past two decades of mass (Youths) migration from Nigeria to other countries across the world. The factors that cause Nigerian youth to leave the country include demographic pressures, political instability, bad governance, low economic performance, poor healthcare system, poor public order, poor educational facilities and high poverty levels. Unemployment is the major driver of migration which is profoundly concentrated among young people. In line with this, Mahmoud and Trebesch in Umar, Godwin and Ogbu (2018) argued, and point to legislation and law enforcement, bribery and corruption, insufficient education, the frightening economic and political instability, crises, etc may as well be a push for migration trend. This is because opportunities for job mobility, business ventures, personal leisure/relaxation and greener pastures may be opened outside the frontiers of a nation's domestic boundary, etc

Education is pivotal in every form of development agenda because it is the hub upon which several other programs revolve. The development of a country depends on the attention paid to the kind of education her citizens acquire. A country economy grows when education becomes a top priority of the government and the private sectors among other needs. Kareem, Gazali, and Adeyefa (2013) assert that quality education required by citizens for fast development of a nation especially technical, vocational education and training (TVET) programmes,

The definition of TVET programmes which surrounds the subject of this paper defines TVET "as a comprehensive term referring to those aspects of the educational process involving, in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related sciences, and the acquisition of core practical skills, attitudes, understanding and knowledge relating to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life." (UNESCO, in Adekunle, 2017), Okwelle, Beako, and Ajie (2017) asserted that TVET is widely recognized as the effective means of developing and empowering the citizenry to stimulate sustainable national development, industrialization, enhance employment, improve the quality of life, reduce poverty, limit the incidence of social vices due to joblessness and promote a culture of peace, freedom and democracy this is to say that it is not education for the sake of it but functional education that propels a nation on the path of development, progress, security, and greatness. TVET holds the key to the profile of Nigeria industrialization just as it has done to many industrialized nations. Technical and vocational education and training (TVET) has emerged as one of the most effective human resource development strategies that developing countries and particularly Nigeria need to embrace in order to train the technical capabilities of its citizens and workforce for rapid industrialization and national economic growth. Pavlova (2014) suggest that TVET plays a crucial role in the social and economic development of every nation. Afeti and Adubra (2015) acknowledges that knowledge and skills are the key drivers of all economies, they oil the wheels of industry and commerce.

Developing a skilled human resource for the growth and transformation of nations' economies is thus a major development issue. Afeti (2017) explains that since the beginning of the new millennium, a fresh awareness of the critical role that TVET can play in economic growth and national development has dawned among policy makers in many African countries especially Nigeria. TVET has the primary objective of providing platform for acquisition of not only employable skills for the world of work or for job creation but also for social life. The unemployed economically active youth population in Nigeria need to be engaged in productive ventures to help make significant contributions to the national economy, industrialization, and overcome their vulnerability to anti-social forces that use them for activities against the security and

peace of the country. They need access to quality education to cultivate skills needed for employment, jobs creation (UNESCO, 2012) as well as decent living.

TVET is aimed at supporting the government's strategies to reducing poverty and achieve socio-economic development for all Nigerians through imparting of technical skills to ensure continuing improvement in national productivity; creation of jobs in the formal and non-formal sectors; an increase in agricultural productivity to create jobs in rural areas; etc UNESCO in Paryono (2017) One of the most important features of TVET is its orientation towards the world of work and the emphasis of the curriculum on the acquisition of employable skills. TVET delivery systems are therefore well placed to train the skilled and entrepreneurial workforce that Nigeria needs to create wealth and reduce poverty. Pongo et al. (2014) suggests that an important characteristic of TVET is that it can be delivered at different levels. This means that TVET can respond, not only to the needs of different types of industries, but also to the different training needs of learners from different socio-economic and academic backgrounds, and prepare them for gainful employment and sustainable livelihoods. A skilled workforce is a basic requirement for driving the engine of industrialization and economic growth, and TVET holds the key to building this type of technical and entrepreneurial workforce (Afeti 2017).

In-line with this assertion, Chandra in Benedicte, Ngah, & Tabi (2022), industrialization can be defined as the increase in the value added of the manufacturing sector as a percentage of GDP. In this regard, the achievement of industrialization implies a faster growth registered in the manufacturing sector relative to other sectors. For Echaudemaison (2014) industrialization is observed through the increase in the share of the secondary sector in terms of employment generation and strong GDP growth. However, the experience of now industrialized countries shows that technical vocational education and training (TVET) plays an important role in the production of skilled personnel working in small and medium enterprises, it focuses on the underpinning industry practices and production processes required to manufacture products in a variety of industries, including aero skills, automotive, building and construction, engineering, furnishing and plastics (Chete, Adeoti, Adeyinka & Ogundele, 2016). It remains one practical way to meaningfully engage the youth in more productive economic activities. The majority of learning is done through manufacturing tasks that relates to business and that promotes adaptable, competent, self-motivated and safe individuals who can work with colleagues to solve problems and complete practical work. By doing manufacturing tasks, participants develop transferable skills relevant to a range of industry based electives and future employment opportunities. They understand industry practices, interpret specifications, including plans, drawings, demonstrate and apply safe practical production process with hand/power tools and machinery. Afeti and Adubra (2018) acknowledges that knowledge and skills are the key drivers of most economies. They oil the wheels of industry and commerce Ogundu and Saue (2019) put it that TVET is the wheel that moves an economy towards progression and transmit knowledge, information and skills from one generation to another, as well human economic empowerment. It has the ability to develop human resources that would improve industrialization thereby enhance youth economic empowerment.

Basically, youth empowerment encompasses the acquisition of skills for establishment of small and medium scale enterprises which can lead to industrialization and economic growth of a state or nation, the objective of empowering the youths according to Azuogu (2017) are to enable them to develop good work ethics, gain entrepreneurship experience, attain employment readiness to develop skills and competence that will enable them to make positive contribution to development of their communities, foster the eradication of poverty amongst young people. Youth economic empowerment is a major challenge in Rivers state today, on this, Echezue and Iweka (2019) reports that the objective of empowering the youths in Nigeria have not yielded much positive results. The economic foundation of every nation is the education of its young people. Mwaura and Kapha (2016) states the way the youth of any nation is brought up and educated in the society determines the future prospect of that nation. River state, which has among others states the youngest population in Nigeria and a huge population growth rate since the 2000s, should exploit and enhance its human capital development for its industrialization and economic diversification, empowerment and growth needs.

Problem of the Study

States in Nigeria today is confronted with the challenges of improving the capacity of their workforce to respond to national development needs and to the demands of a rapidly changing, and more globally competitive world. Rivers state has a projected population of over 7 million, making it the fourth largest population in Nigeria, and the first largest in south-south, (National Population Commission, 2021). River state has an economically active and working age population that is over 50% of entire population and an unemployment rate of 14.2%. The dominant population group is 15-50 years (55.5%)

(National Bureau of Statistics, 2017). Unemployment and under-employment in Nigeria is highest among those aged between 15-34. The national unemployment rate of 18.7% is far higher than the International Labour Organization's (ILO) global unemployment rate of 7.2% for the same period (National Bureau of Statistics, 2017). The high rate of unemployment in Nigeria has been linked to lack of relevant practical skills, which can only be reduced through skills acquisition (Dike, 2019). Recent data released by the National Bureau of Statistics (2017) shows that the problem of unemployment has continued to be on the increase. In spite of the huge human and material resources, many Nigerians youths believe they were better off at independence in 1960 than they are currently. It is precisely the feeling of a dismal future that fuels the desperation of people (youths) seeking greener pastures abroad for both skilled and unskilled—men and women alike. Ever since the industrial revolution in the late 18th century, progress and prosperity have been closely identified with economic development (Jomo in Okorieocha and Taneh, 2013). The economic competitiveness of a country depends on the skills of its workforce. The skills and competencies of the workforce. In-turn are dependent upon the quality of the country's education and training systems Rao in Okorieocha and Taneh (2013) asserts that to enhance productivity, stimulate competitiveness, and bring about economic development, youths skill development is important. Skill training is critical for sustainable industrialization and poverty reduction in terms of creating a critical mass of technically and entrepreneurially qualified people who are able to stimulate investment opportunities, create jobs and increase productivity. A well-educated and trained work force is a prerequisite for harnessing the potential of competitiveness, economic development and industrialization which in-turn will contribute positively to curbing youth migration to overseas.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to examine curbing youth migration through sustainable industrialization and economic empowerment in Rivers State; the role of technical and vocational education and training programmes. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Investigate the causes of youth migration in Rivers State.
2. Examine the economic empowerment role of TVET in curbing youth migration in Rivers State.
3. Examine the Industrial role of TVET in curbing youth migration in Rivers State.

Research Questions

1. What are the causes of youth migration in Rivers State?
2. What are the economic empowerment role of TVET in curbing youth migration in Rivers State?
3. What are the industrial role of TVET in curbing youth migration Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean responses of technical education lectures and final year students on the causes of youth migration in River State.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean responses of technical education lecturers and final year students on the economic empowerment role of TVET in curbing youth migration in Rivers State.
3. There is no significant difference between the mean responses of technical education lecturers and final year students on the industrial roles of TVET in curbing youth migration in Rivers State

2. METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in Rivers State. The study adopted descriptive survey design. The population of the study comprised all the technical education lecturers and final year technical education students in the three higher institutions in Rivers State that offer technical and vocational education and training programmes. They are, Rivers State University, Port Harcourt (13 lecturers, 47 final year Students); Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt (35 lecturers, 45 final year students) and Federal College of Education (Technical), Omoku, Rivers State in affiliation with University of Nigeria Nsukka, (52 lecturers and 56 final year students). Final students were selected because they have spent more time in the

school than other set of students. As at the time of the study, there was population of 100 and 148 technical education lecturers and final year students respectively. The population was manageable; therefore, the entire population was used for the study. Self-made survey questionnaire titled “Roles of TVET in Curbing Youth Migration (RTVETCYM)” served as the instrument for data collection. The instrument was partitioned into two sections that were structured in four point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA-4), Agree (A-3), Disagree (D-2) and Strongly Disagree (SD-1). The instrument was face validated by two experts in the Department of Vocational and Technology Education in Rivers State University. Also, the instrument was tested to ascertain its reliability using Cronbach Alpha Reliability Coefficient tool. This was achieved through purposive sampling of 7 mechanical technology education lecturers in Niger Delta University, Bayelsa. The reliability coefficient achieved was 0.74 which confirmed the reliability of the instrument. Copies of the instruments were administered and retrieved by the researcher on the spot of administration. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and to ascertain the homogeneity of responses. Also, z-test statistical tool was used to test the hypotheses. Mean score less than 2.50 were rejected while Mean scores equal or greater than 2.50 were accepted. Also, z-calculated values less than z-critical values were accepted while z-calculated values greater than z-critical values were rejected which shows that there was a significant difference between the mean responses of the groups.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Research Question 1. What are the causes of youth migration to overseas in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean Responses on the Causes of Youth Migration

S/N	Item	Lecturers (n=100)		Students (n=144)			
		X1	SD	Decision	X	SD	Decision
1	Insecurity	3.81	.71	Agree	3.70	.46	Agree
2	Bad governance	3.40	.61	Agree	3.38	.48	Agree
3	Poor economic performance	3.72	.62	Agree	3.22	.72	Agree
4	Poor health-care system	3.23	.49	Agree	3.72	.59	Agree
5	Poor public order	3.02	.69	Agree	3.20	.49	Agree
6	Poor educational system/facilities	3.54	.65	Agree	3.35	.96	Agree
7	Lack of industries	3.89	.30	Agree	3.85	.35	Agree
8	High poverty level	3.25	.43	Agree	3.17	.48	Agree
9	Poor economic policy Implementation	3.05	.71	Agree	3.88	.32	Agree
10	Youth unemployment	3.48	.54	Agree	3.27	.57	Agree
11	Weak Industrial Policy	3.25	.46	Agree	2.96	.93	Agree
12	Bribery and Corruption	3.58	.49	Agree	3.33	.85	Agree
	Total	3.08	.67	Agree	3.42	.60	Agree

Source, Field Survey 2023

Table 1 on the causes of youth migration to overseas in Rivers State shows that lecturers and final year students agreed that all the items highlighted are factors that contribute to youth migration to overseas. This is based on the grand mean score of 3.08 and 3.42 respectively which is above 2.50 that was earlier stated as the acceptable means. Also, the grand mean score for each of the items shows a high level of acceptance for each of the items by each group. Furthermore, the closeness in the standard deviation for the two groups which is .67 and .60 shows homogeneity in their responses. This findings is in line with the assertion that Unemployment is the major driver of migration which is profoundly concentrated among young people.in

Research Question 2. What are the economic empowerment roles of TVET in mitigating youth migration in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean Responses on the Economic Empowerment Role of TVET

S/N	Item	Lecturers (n=100)		Students (n=144)			
		X1	SD	Decision	X	SD	Decision
1	It equip youths with requisite knowledge, skills & attitude for occupation in the communities	3.42	.49	Agree	3.11	1.19	Agree
2	Employment creation in both rural and urban areas	3.61	.48	Agree	3.23	.48	Agree
3	It improves the living condition and income generation of the youths	3.31	.68	Agree	3.39	.55	Agree
4	Youths with tvet skills can establish & manage small & medium scale Industries	3.23	.51	Agree	3.41	.77	Agree
5	Provides competence that will enable each graduate to adapt to the knowledge based society	3.79	.40	Agree	3.15	.49	Agree
6	It reduces the rate of dependency ratio amongst youths	3.75	.43	Agree	3.87	.33	Agree
7	It promote youths entrepreneurship	3.73	.44	Agree	3.22	.53	Agree
8	Strengthens the role & effectiveness of tvet trainees	3.17	.62	Agree	2.86	1.10	Agree
9	Addresses skill mismatch	3.78	.41	Agree	3.30	.68	Agree
10	Empowers youths to participate in the workforce	3.74	.43	Agree	3.21	.63	Agree
11	It turns lazy and unbecoming youths into productive workforce	3.66	.52	Agree	3.21	.63	Agree
12	It gives the youths opportunities for investment and asset acquisition	3.22	.88	Agree	3.99	.98	Agree
13	It widens opportunities for people to find job which fits into their talents and preferences	3.61	.48	Agree	3.23	.84	Agree
	Total	3.59	.50	Agree	3.08	.74	Agree

Source. Field Survey, 2023

Table 2 on the economic empowerment role of technical and vocational education and training programmes in mitigating youth migration in Rivers State shows that lecturers and final year students agreed that all the items highlighted are the economic empowerment roles that TVET plays in curbing youth migration to overseas in Rivers State. This is based on the grand mean score of 3.59 and 3.08 respectively which is above 2.50 that was earlier stated as the acceptable means. Also, the grand mean score for each of the items shows a high level of acceptance for each of the items by each group. Furthermore, the closeness of the standard deviation for the two groups which is .50 and .74 shows homogeneity in their responses. This findings is in line with the findings of Ogundu and Saue (2019) put it that TVET is the wheel that moves an economy towards progression and transmit knowledge, information and skills from one generation to another, as well human economic empowerment. It has the ability to develop human resources that would improve industrialization thereby enhance youth economic empowerment.

Research Question 3. What are the Industrial role of TVET in curbing youth migration in Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean Responses on the Industrial Role of TVET

S/N	Item	Lecturers (n=100)		Students (n=144)			
		X1	SD	Decision	X	SD	Decision
1	It aim at supporting government strategies on industrialization	3.58	.49	Agree	3.42	.57	Agree
2	tv et aim at producing industrialist	3.38	.52	Agree	3.23	.66	Agree
3	It holds the key to the profile of a country's industrial development	3.73	.44	Agree	3.39	.64	Agree
4	It propel a nation on the path of development, peace, & progress	3.31	.58	Agree	3.22	.61	Agree
5	tv et paves way for quality education & skill acquisition for industrial development	3.52	.50	Agree	3.01	.66	Agree
6	Increases the productivity and Profitability of the industrial business	3.41	.49	Agree	3.62	.66	Agree
7	It create platform for the production of skill workers for industrial development	3.27	.47	Agree	3.41	.96	Agree
8	It is a source for industrial Transformation	3.43	.49	Agree	2.97	.76	Agree
9	It enhances industrial competitiveness In the global economy	3.41	.53	Agree	3.22	.98	Agree
10	It offers training to individuals in areas like auto repairs, building, Metalwork, woodwork, elect/elect Technology which can lead to industrialization of a state	3.87	.33	Agree	3.28	1.09	Agree
Total		3.49	.48	Agree	3.28	.76	Agree

Source, Field Survey, 2023

Table 3 on the Industrial role of technical and vocational education and training programmes in curbing youth migration in Rivers State shows that lecturers and final year students agreed that all the items highlighted are the industrial roles that TVET plays in curbing youth migration to overseas in Rivers State. This is based on the grand mean score of 3.49 and 3.28 respectively which is above 2.50 that was earlier mentioned as the acceptable means. Also, the grand mean score for each of the items shows a high level of acceptance for each of the items by each group. Furthermore, the closeness of the standard deviation for the two groups which is .48 and .76 shows the homogeneity in their responses. This findings is in line with the findings of Chete, Adeoti, Adeyinka, & Ogundele (2016) that the experience of now industrialized countries shows that technical and vocational education and training programmes plays an important role in the production of skilled personnel working in small and medium enterprises, it focuses on the underpinning industry practices and production processes required to manufacture products in a variety of industries, including aero skills, automotive, building and construction, engineering, furnishing and plastics.

Hypothesis 1.

There is no significant difference between the mean responses of technical education lectures and final year students on the causes of youth migration to overseas in River State.

Table 4: z-Test Analysis on the causes of youth migration to overseas in Rivers State

Category	n	\bar{X}	SD	DF	z-cal	z-crit	Remark
Lecturers	100	3.08	0.67	24	4.07	1.96	Significant
Final Year Students	144	3.42	0.60				

Source: *Researchers' field survey, 2023*

Data in table 4 above reveal that z-calculated (4.07) is greater than z-critical (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, hence there is a great significant difference between the mean responses of technical education lecturers and final year students on the causes of youth migration to overseas in River State.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significance difference between the mean responses of technical education lecturers and final year students on the human economic empowerment role of TVET in curbing youth migration in Rivers State.

Table 5: t-Test Analysis on the economic empowerment role of technical and vocational education and training in curbing youth migration in Rivers State.

Category	n	\bar{x}	SD	DF	z-cal	z-crit	Remark
Lecturers	100	3.59	0.50	24	6.42	1.96	Significant
Final Year Students	144	3.08	0.74				

Source: *Researchers' field survey, 2023*

Data in table 5 above reveal that z-calculated (6.42) is greater than z-critical (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, hence there is a great significant difference between the mean responses of technical education lecturers and final year students on the human economic empowerment role of technical and vocational education and training programmes in curbing youth migration in Rivers State.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significance difference between the mean responses of technical education lecturers and final year students on the industrial roles of TVET in curbing youth migration in Rivers State

Table 6: z-Test Analysis on the industrial role of technical and vocational education and training programmes in curbing youth migration in Rivers State

Category	N	\bar{x}	SD	DF	z-cal	z-crit	Remark
Lecturers	100	3.49	0.48	24	2.64	1.96	Significant
Final Year Students	144	3.28	0.76				

Source: *Researchers' field survey, 2023*

Data in table 5 above reveal that z-calculated (2.64) is greater than z-critical (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected, hence there is a great significant difference between the mean responses of technical education lecturers and final year students on the industrial roles of technical and vocational education and training programmes in curbing youth migration in Rivers State

4. CONCLUSION

From the findings, this study concluded that tvet could play a significant role in curbing youth migration from the state as it has revealed the causes of youth migration which one of the causes is insecurity, lack of industry, poverty, poor economic performance, and it has also shown that technical and vocational education and training programmes play a significance role in economic empowerment of youths as it helps and empower youths to participate in the workforce and gives the opportunity to acquire assets. it also reveal and concluded that plays significant roles in the industrialization of a state as it helps to offer training to individuals in areas like auto repairs, building, Metalwork, woodwork, elect/elect Technology which can lead to industrialization of a state, create platform for the production of skill workers for industrial development etc Finally, Many developed countries in the world, realize the significant role technical and vocational education and training programmes plays in equipping individuals with relevant skills and knowledge, enabling them to effectually participate in social, economic, industrialized and technological innovation processes, Technical and vocational education and training programmes can play a vital role in economic development/empowerment, and poverty reduction if due attention is given it.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

From the findings of the study, the following recommendations are deduced:

1. Government should as a matter of urgency adequately fund and equip technical and vocational education and training programmes with up-to-date equipment to ensure that TVET students are well prepared before graduation, as that will ensure their self-employment as well making them to think less of migration to overseas
2. There should be more emphasis on practical activities than theoretical to empower the graduates (youths) skillfully for self-employment as well empowerment
3. Nigeria's government leaders must cultivate a youth-friendly socioeconomic environment and support them by providing technical know-how, resources, mentorship, financial and practical support they need to thrive in the Nigerian economy
4. Government should make provision for soft loan for all TVET graduate to assess for establishment of small and medium industries or workshops as to get them engaged, and empowered immediately after graduation

REFERENCES

- [1] Adekunle, O. (2017) Prospects for TVET in Developing Skills for Work in Nigeria, *Journal of Education and Practice* 8(21) 101-109
- [2] Afeti, G. (2017). Technical and Vocational Education and Training for Industrialization. The African Research and Resource Forum: Occasional Paper; Kenya.
- [3] Afeti, G. & Adubra A. L. (2018) Lifelong Technical and Vocational Skills development for Sustainable Socioeconomic Growth in Africa: Association for the Development of Education in Africa: Burkina Faso.
- [4] Afi, P.N. & Obinnim, E. (2015) Changing Landscape of Industry Practice: The Role of Quality Technical Vocational Education and Training in Ghana. *Journal of Art and Design Studies* 3 (2) 1-8.
- [5] Akinyemi, A.I., and Mobolaji, J.W. (2022). 21st July, 2022. *Premium Times Newspaper*. Large youth population could be an asset or a Burden
- [6] Azuogu, N.O. (2017) Youth empowerment programme in Nigeria: Issues and challenges Retrieve 21st January, 2024 on-line from www.african-union
- [7] Benedicte, D.; Ngah, A. & Tabi, H.N. (2022) Technical Education, Vocational Training and Industrialization in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), *Journal of Sustainable Development* 15(1) 65-81
- [8] Chete, L.N., Adeoti, J. O., Adeyinka, F.M. & Ogundele, O. (2016). Industrial Development and Growth in Nigeria: Lessons and Challenges. *Learning to Complite Working Paper*. 8, 3-5

- [9] Echezu, A. & Iweka (2019). Technical and vocational education and training: As effective means of youth empowerment in Nigeria. *Journal of Research in National Development Niger Delta Journal of Education*, 10(1), 15-30'
- [10] Mwaura, N.C. & Kapha, O. (2016). The Role of Technical and Vocational Institutions in Empowerment of Youths in Gitaru Ward, Kabete Constituency, Kiambu County. *International Journal of Management and Commerce Innovations* 4(2) 494-500
- [11] National Bureau of Statistics, N. (2017). Unemployment/Under-Employment Report (Q4 2016), (April).
- [12] Niche, (2014). Strategy on Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) Netherlands: Nuffic.
- [13] Okorieocha, C. N. & Taneh, N. A. (2013) Roles of TVET in Industrialization and Economic Development of Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Education Research* 1(1) 1-7
- [14] Okwelle, P.C.; Beako, Y.T. & Ajie, P.M. (2017), Technical Skills Needed by Motor Vehicle Mechanics Apprenticeship to Establish Standard Motor Mechanic Enterprise in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State, *International Journal of Innovative Scientific & Engineering Technology Research* 5(4); 27-34
- [15] Organisation of Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) (2015). Reviews of vocational education and training: Learning for Jobs. Pointers for policy development Directorate for Education, Education and Training Policy Division.
- [16] Pongo, N. A., Effah, B., Osei-Owusu, B., Obinnim, E. & Sam, F. (2014). The Impact of TVET on Ghana's Socio-Economic Development: A Case Study of ICCES TVET Skills Training in Two Regions of Ghana *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, 4(1), 185-192.
- [17] Smita, D. & Mallah, V. (2015), Migration: causes and effects. *Journal of Business and management* 5(4) 228-236
- [18] Umar, K.; Godwin, M.; & Ogbu, C. (2018) A Study of Illegal Migration Trends and the Pull and Push Factors in Nigeria, 2011 – 2017. *World journal of Innovation Research* 5(6), 53-60
- [19] UNESCO-UNEVOC. (2012). *World TVET Database Nigeria*. Germany. Retrieved from www.unevoc.unesco.org.
- [20] Uba, C., & Chiuwike, H. (2022). 8th April, 2022 *Blue Print Newspaper* Younger Nigerians agitate, who is a youth?.